

Importance of Copyright Protection

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Abstract: This article explains what copyright is, as well as what conditions must be met for granting copyright to the result of the intellect created by the author. In addition, it will be discussed in detail what opportunities its protection gives to the author, how important it is for the copyright protection for the development of the state.

Keywords: Copyright, intellektual activity, uniqueness of the object, originality, expression in an objective form.

Introduction.

Intellectual activity is the creative activity of a person. It is not difficult to understand this from the dictionary meaning of the word intellect. INTELLECT means mind in Latin. It is mainly the product of the work of intellectual workers - writers, poets, artists, scientists, engineers, technicians and other intellectual workers.

Copyright is one of the areas of law that protects works created by a person as a result of creative and intellectual activity. Copyright gives the author such rights, as a result of which the author has the right to control the use, distribution and reproduction of the work created by his intellectual activity.

The main part.

In order for the author to have the copyright for his work, he must fulfill certain conditions:

The first of these is that the work created by the author must be a product of creativity, that is, it must be original. That is, in order for a person to have the author's right to his work, he must have created this work with his own intellectual labor, and he must not resort to any other illegal ways and commit acts that violate the law.

Second, the created work must be unique. That is, the work created by the author should not resemble the result of such type of intellect created before. If we look at it logically, if the created work is similar to the result of the previous type of intellect, it leads to the conclusion that the author who created the second created it as a result of his intellectual work, but copied it from the previous one.

Thirdly, the created work must be expressed in some objective form. Otherwise, this intellectual result cannot be copyrighted. Because the idea belongs to everyone until it is implemented. Although you have a detailed map of the creation of a certain invention in your mind, you cannot defend it if you have not expressed it in an objective way.

Now let's discuss why copyright protection is necessary, which is considered the most relevant part of our article.

It is also known from what we mentioned above that the copyright is given to the result of intellectual activity of a person. It can be seen that such an intellectual process lasts a long time. Creating an object of authorship requires a lot of time and mental work of the author.

Usually, objects of intellectual property are considered very sensitive in relation to goods: as soon as its essence becomes known to the general public, the intellectual property owner becomes in need of special protection. If the state does not protect, this facility can be appropriated by anyone who has the necessary means to use it for profit. Therefore, if after such a long intellectual work there is no guaranteed legal protection of the intellectual result of the author, the person who has spent a certain amount of money on the development of intellectual property objects cannot even deduct his expenses, and as a result, he is not interested in this type of activity. because of which he loses interest. According to V. I. Yermenko, the absolute right encourages the development of artistic creativity and scientific and technical development in the society¹.

Non-protection of copyright not only reduces the author's incentive to create a work, but also slows down the development of the state in a certain sense. Because inventions created by scientists contribute to the development of the country. Let's take the invention of the light bulb as a simple example. As a result of this intellect, the environment can be illuminated at night, and people can work hard at night as well as during the day.

Therefore, every country has strengthened the protection of copyright in its legal system. In particular, the fact that the protection of intellectual property by law is established in Article 53 of our constitution, which is considered our main constitution, is a proof of our statement.

Summary.

In conclusion, we can say that the protection of intellectual property by the state is not only a means for a person who has spent his money, time and mental work on the result of intellectual activity, but also an incentive for his future activity.

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